

Nvath-like Cp_0hpf: 36.17

Nvhes3 Cp_0hpf: 35.77

NvfoxD3 Cp_0hpf: 40.00

Nvsox10-like Cp_0hpf: 34.80

Nvfoxq2-like3 Cp_0hpf: 33.31

Nvsox2 Cp_0hpf: 40.00

Nvcoup-like1 Cp_0hpf: 40.00

Nvcoup-like2 Cp_0hpf: 33.31

Nvgfi-like Cp_0hpf: 38.94

Nvhd145 Cp_0hpf: 40.00

Nvtailless-like Cp_0hpf: 38.52

Nvvsx-like Cp_0hpf: 34.11

Nvelav-like Cp_0hpf: 28.66

Nvdkk3-like Cp_0hpf: 36.65

Nvpea3-like Cp_0hpf: 36.87

NvpaxA Cp_0hpf: 31.57

Nvgcm Cp_0hpf: 40.00

NvashA Cp_0hpf: 40.00

Nvvegfl-like1 Cp_0hpf: 29.38

Nvhox2 Cp_0hpf: 40.00

Nvhd052 Cp_0hpf: 37.65

